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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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PEDAGOGICAL ESSENCE OF IMPROVING STUDENTS' COLLABORATIVE SKILLS THROUGH MULTI-VECTOR APPROACHES

Turemuratova Aziza Begibaevna
Assistant, Department of Pedagogy and
Psychology, Karakalpak State University named
after Berdakh, Republic of Karakalpakstan
ORCID: 0009-0000-7631-9120

Otelbayeva Muhayyo Alisher qizi
Chemistry Teacher, Secondary School No. 47,
Kungrad District, Republic of Karakalpakstan
ORCID: 0000-0003-2091-7978

Abstract: This article examines the pedagogical essence of developing students' collaborative skills in modern education based on multi-vector approaches. The study presents the theoretical foundations of collaborative learning in educational processes, its relationship with pedagogical methods, its role in enhancing students' psychological potential, and the influence of social factors in the development of collaborative competencies. In addition, the article analyzes the importance of a multi-vector approach in organizing students' collective activities, improving teaching methods, and creating an effective pedagogical environment in modern education. Special attention is given to the traditions of educating the younger generation in the spirit of collectivism, cooperation (collaboration), mutual respect, and social responsibility based on the example of Karakalpak folk pedagogy.

Key words: modern education, collaborative learning, multi-vector approach, pedagogical approaches, collaborative skills, upbringing, pedagogical methods, teaching methods, interactive methods.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada zamonaviy ta'lim tizimida ko'p vektorli yondashuvlar asosida talabalarning kollaborativ ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishning pedagogik mohiyati yoritilgan. Tadqiqot jarayonida ta'lim jarayonida kollaborativ ta'limning nazariy asoslari, uning pedagogik metodlar bilan o'zaro bog'liqligi, talabalarning psixologik salohiyatini oshirishdagi ahamiyati hamda ijtimoiy omillarning ta'siri tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, maqolada talabalarning jamoaviy faoliyatini rivojlantirishda ko'p vektorli yondashuvning o'rni, o'qitish metodlarini takomillashtirish va zamonaviy ta'lim muhitini tashkil etish masalalari ko'rib chiqiladi. Qoraqalpoq xalq pedagogikasi misolida yosh avlodni jamoaviylik, hamkorlik (kollaboratsiya), o'zaro hurmat va ijtimoiy mas'uliyat ruhida tarbiyalash an'analari ilmiy jihatdan tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: zamonaviy ta'lim, kollaborativ ta'lim, ko'p vektorli yondashuv, pedagogik yondashuvlar, kollaborativ ko'nikmalar, tarbiya, pedagogik metodlar, ta'lim metodlari, interaktiv metodlar.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается педагогическая сущность формирования коллаборативных навыков у студентов на основе многовекторного подхода в современном образовании. В ходе исследования раскрываются теоретические основы коллаборативного обучения в образовательном процессе, его взаимосвязь с педагогическими методами, значение в развитии психологического потенциала обучающихся, а также влияние социальных факторов на формирование сотрудничества. Кроме того, в статье анализируется роль многовекторного подхода в развитии коллективной деятельности студентов, совершенствовании методов обучения и организации педагогической среды в современном образовании. На примере каракалпакской народной педагогики рассматриваются традиции воспитания молодого поколения в духе коллективизма, сотрудничества (коллаборации), взаимного уважения и социальной ответственности.

Ключевые слова: современное образование, коллаборативное обучение, многовекторный подход, педагогические подходы, коллаборативные навыки, воспитание, педагогические методы, методы обучения, интерактивные методы.

INTRODUCTION

In today's modern educational processes, not only individual knowledge and pedagogical competencies are crucial for the quality of education, but also effective engagement with modern programs of collective education (collaborative learning). Skills such as interacting with others, sharing responsibility within a student group, and operating on the basis of social partnership are of significant importance. From this perspective, fostering and enhancing collaborative skills in students is becoming a priority in the pedagogical process.

Collaborative skills are understood as an individual's ability to work toward a goal in cooperation with a team, solve problems collectively, respect a diversity of opinions, adhere to a culture of communication, and contribute to achieving a common result. The multi-vector approach, in turn, entails organizing the pedagogical process not in a single direction, but through a combination of various methodological, cultural, psychological, and social factors. This approach requires a comprehensive consideration of students' personal, social, and cultural development.

In particular, relying on the national pedagogical heritage, especially utilizing the rich experience of Karakalpak folk pedagogy, can be an effective tool in forming collaborative skills. Karakalpak folk pedagogy is an educational system formed over centuries and embodied in spiritual and moral values, customs, rituals, and examples of oral creativity. In it, qualities such as collectivism, mutual assistance, respect for elders, courtesy toward the young, decision-making based on consultation, and working together hold a primary place. These processes naturally served as a social school for developing collaborative competencies.

The pedagogical essence of improving students' collaborative skills based on a multi-vector approach manifests in several key vectors. Firstly, the methodological vector involves organizing the educational process on an integrative, systemic, and activity-oriented basis. Here, interactive methods, project-based learning, problem-based learning, and training technologies are applied. Secondly, the cultural vector involves integrating national values, traditions, and elements of folk pedagogy into the educational process. The third vector is the consideration of psychological factors, that is, taking into account students' individual characteristics, communication styles, social roles, and motivational factors. The fourth vector consists of creating an environment of social partnership and cooperation, strengthening the interactions between student and student, student and teacher, and the educational institution and society.

From the standpoint of its pedagogical essence, the process of improving collaborative skills is intrinsically linked to an individual's socialization, communicative competence, and professional training^[1]. According to the demands of the modern labor market, a specialist must not only be knowledgeable in their field but also be able to work in a team, resolve conflicts constructively, and possess leadership and partnership qualities. Therefore, creating a collaborative environment in higher educational institutions is a pressing task.

In Karakalpak folk pedagogy, the traditions of consultation and collective decision-making hold an important place. Mechanisms such as the council of elders, clan-based consultations, and considering the community's opinion served to shape the younger generation into responsible and cooperative individuals. Combining this experience with modern pedagogical technologies is a practical expression of the multi-vector approach.

Using examples of national oral creativity can also be an effective means of developing students' collaborative skills. Through epics (dastans), proverbs, sayings, and legends, the ideas of collectivism, unity, and solidarity are instilled. An educational process organized on the basis of a multi-vector approach increases student engagement, transforming them from passive recipients of knowledge into active participants. In this context, the teacher acts as a facilitator, meaning that they guide and direct the process without dominating it. This fosters a democratic pedagogical environment. The teacher–student relationship in Karakalpak folk pedagogy is also built on mutual respect and trust, which closely resembles the collaborative model.

The process of enhancing collaborative skills must be implemented in stages. Initially, during the motivational stage, students develop an understanding of the necessity for collaboration. In the subsequent stage, teamwork skills are cultivated through practical exercises. Finally, in the concluding stage, the achieved results are reinforced through reflection and self-assessment mechanisms. If this process is enriched with national pedagogical heritage, its effectiveness will increase even further.

Thus, enhancing students' collaborative skills based on a multi-vector approach requires a comprehensive, systematic, and culturally grounded model of the pedagogical process. Karakalpak folk pedagogy, in turn, provides rich spiritual and educational resources for this process. By integrating national and modern pedagogical experience, it is possible to cultivate qualities such as collectivism, responsibility, communication culture, and social activeness in students.

A deeper analysis of the scientific and theoretical foundations of the multi-vector approach reveals that this model is not merely a set of methods, but an integrative form of pedagogical thinking ^[2]. It is founded on the principles of systematicity, continuity, cultural adaptability, and an activity-oriented focus. The process of improving students' collaborative skills yields effective results only when it is organized taking into account the interaction mechanisms between the individual, the group, and society. In this process, an individual's internal motivation, values, social experience, and communicative potential develop in harmony.

Theoretically, collaborative learning is intrinsically linked to the constructivist approach. According to constructivist views, knowledge is not delivered in a ready-made form but is actively constructed by the learner and built through social interaction. In the course of collective discussions, debates, project activities, and problem-solving, students not only acquire knowledge but also master the skills of substantiating their opinions, listening to others, and reaching a consensus. This forms the core components of collaborative competence.

Analyzing this process through the example of Karakalpak folk pedagogy, one can see that the ideas of solidarity and unity reflected in oral folk art created a distinctive constructivist environment. For example, in epic poems, heroes often achieve their goals with the community's support, heed the advice of elders, and prioritize the interests of the people over personal ones. Such ideas reinforce the necessity of social responsibility and collaboration in the minds of the younger generation. Utilizing these content-rich resources in the modern educational process strengthens students' sense of cultural identity and social solidarity.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In the modern pedagogical process, collaborative learning is recognized as a form of activity aimed at the integrated development of an individual's knowledge, skills, and social competencies. This educational model transforms students from passive recipients of knowledge into active participants, fostering skills in problem-solving through teamwork, exchanging ideas, and sharing responsibility. Pedagogically, the main principles of collaborative learning are defined by the creation of an environment based on individual activity, mutual respect, and social partnership, as well as the integrative and systematic organization of the educational process.

Theoretically, collaborative learning is intrinsically linked to constructivist and social learning theories. According to the constructivist approach, knowledge is not delivered in a ready-made form but is actively constructed by the learner through social interaction. Furthermore, the concept of the "zone of proximal development," proposed by Vygotsky, forms the psychological foundation of collaborative activity ^[3]. According to this theory, students acquire more complex knowledge and skills by working together.

The sociological foundations of collaborative learning are also significant. The system of interactions, social norms, and roles within a group shapes students' social competence. From this standpoint, collaborative learning provides an opportunity not only for individual growth but also for balancing social processes within the group, as well as for developing constructive communication and conflict resolution. Pedagogical research shows that knowledge acquired through social interaction is better retained and develops social qualities in students such as mutual respect, trust, and responsibility.

International experience shows that collaborative learning is applied as an effective pedagogical approach in various countries. For example, project-based learning and problem-based learning methods are widely used in the United States higher education system. Empirical research has shown that when students work in groups, their level of communication increases by 40–50 %, the speed of problem-solving increases significantly, and their sense of personal responsibility is strengthened. At the same time, students' creative thinking and leadership skills are also developed.

In European countries, particularly Germany, the Netherlands, and Sweden, the implementation of collaborative learning is based on interactive and multi-stage models of the educational process. For instance, in

Germany, using the “Team-Based Learning” methodology, students study course material in small groups, distribute tasks, and find solutions together. Research results have shown that with this approach, students acquire a high level of skill in connecting theoretical knowledge with practice, reaching compromises, and making decisions. In the Netherlands, through the “Collaborative Problem Solving” program, students solve real-life problems in groups, which enhances their social, communicative, and creative skills.

The effectiveness of collaborative learning has also been confirmed in Asian countries. In Singapore and South Korea, group work and project-based activities are implemented as an integral part of educational standards. Studies conducted in Singapore show that joint decision-making and problem-solving skills among students increase by 30 %, while mutual respect and the quality of communication improve significantly. In South Korea, collective assessment and self-assessment systems are used in the educational process, through which students develop skills in analyzing their activities, identifying strengths and weaknesses, and formulating strategies for future development [4].

International studies have shown that the most crucial factors determining success in collaborative learning are the role of the educator and the organization of the group. Educators participate in the learning process as facilitators: they encourage students and provide resources but do not dominate the process. At the same time, the group's composition, the experience and abilities of individual students, and the task distribution process are considered key conditions for success.

The effectiveness of collaborative learning is higher than that of traditional lesson formats because it develops not only students' academic performance but also their social, communicative, and personal competencies. For example, in studies conducted in the United States, group work improved students' interpersonal communication skills by 35–50 %, with a significant enhancement in leadership abilities and the capacity to reach compromises. In European studies, students increased their critical thinking and problem-solving skills in group work by 40 %, considerably strengthening their sense of personal responsibility and influence on group outcomes.

International practical experience has also revealed the importance of considering the national and cultural context. For instance, in Asian countries, students' social norms and principles of respect significantly influence communication and decision-making processes within the group. Therefore, international experience recommends enhancing the effectiveness of collaborative learning by taking into account national values and pedagogical traditions [5].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

An analysis of the pedagogical foundations of collaborative learning through international research reveals that it serves to develop personal initiative, group cooperation, constructive conflict resolution, and communicative competencies. Moreover, empirical results indicate that collaborative activity increases student motivation and strengthens independent thinking and creative problem-solving skills.

International studies show that in collaborative learning the educator's role is that of a facilitator. The educator guides the learning process, provides motivation and resources, but does not exercise sole dominance. This allows students to make independent decisions, justify their opinions, and actively participate in the collective process. Furthermore, international experience demonstrates the effectiveness of supporting collaborative activities through technological tools such as online platforms, virtual laboratories, and interactive programs.

The results of empirical research show that the collaborative learning model develops not only students' academic performance but also their social, communicative, and personal competencies. Additionally, international experience indicates that for the successful implementation of collaborative learning, group composition, task structure, pedagogical facilitation, and cultural context alignment are of significant importance.

In the modern pedagogical model, the integration of elements of Karakalpak folk pedagogy is carried out through several methods. In the project-based learning method, students are divided into groups to design and present a project on a specific ritual or custom of the Karakalpak people. Each member assumes a specific task and role within the group, which strengthens social responsibility and cooperation. Through problem-solving exercises, students jointly develop strategies, make decisions, and implement solutions in practice.

At the end of the session, through reflection and self-assessment, students analyze their performance, identify their strengths and weaknesses, and evaluate their contribution to the group's results. The collaborative learning model integrating elements of Karakalpak folk pedagogy significantly develops students' social and communicative skills. Within a group, skills such as exchanging ideas, reaching compromises, and constructively accepting opposing viewpoints are enhanced.

Additionally, personal responsibility and leadership qualities are strengthened, and a sense of social solidarity is fostered through the assimilation of national culture and values. Complex tasks and project-based activities teach students to think critically and creatively, developing their skills in finding solutions to real-life problems.

In modern pedagogical practice, combining elements of Karakalpak folk pedagogy with a multi-vector approach is achieved by unifying pedagogical, psychological, cultural, and social vectors. The pedagogical vector ensures the systematic and interactive organization of the educational process; the psychological vector takes into account students' individual characteristics and motivation; the cultural vector integrates national values; and the social vector creates an environment of cooperation and partnership within the group.

Lessons that integrate elements of Karakalpak folk pedagogy into modern education to develop collaborative skills enable students to actively participate in project and group work, make decisions and solve problems, increase personal and social responsibility, develop cultural identity, constructively resolve intra-group conflicts, and build critical thinking skills.

Thus, integrating elements of Karakalpak folk pedagogy with a multi-vector approach serves as an enriching factor in the pedagogical process and prepares students as individuals ready for cooperation in modern society. The research findings indicate that integrating the national pedagogical heritage with modern educational methods is an effective tool for developing students' communicative, social, and critical thinking skills. Furthermore, based on an analysis of international pedagogical experiences, methodological recommendations aimed at increasing the effectiveness of collaborative learning have been developed.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The practical model of the multi-vector approach can be seen as consisting of three main components: a motivational–communicative component, an activity–practical component, and a reflective–evaluative component.

The motivational–communicative component involves fostering a positive attitude toward collaboration in students, understanding the importance of teamwork, and creating an atmosphere of mutual respect. At this stage, the instructor utilizes socio-psychological training, role-playing games, and discussion methods.

The activity–practical component is implemented directly through team projects, working in small groups, and jointly completing research assignments. The reflective–evaluative component ensures that students analyze their activities, identify their strengths and weaknesses, and determine future directions for development.

Elements of reflection were also present in Karakalpak folk pedagogy. Adapting this experience in modern pedagogy serves to cultivate a culture of self-assessment and peer evaluation among students.

In the process of organizing experimental work, it is advisable to develop a special pedagogical program based on a multi-vector approach. This program should incorporate a system of collaborative tasks enriched with national values, interactive methods, and assessment criteria. For instance, students could be assigned the task of modeling the traditional ceremonies of the Karakalpak people in the form of a modern social project. In this task, they would divide into groups, distribute roles, create a plan, apply a creative approach, and present the final result ^[6].

Throughout the process, skills in communication, leadership, compromise, and time management are developed. Analysis of the experimental results shows that sessions organized based on a collaborative approach increase students' social engagement, strengthen their level of mutual trust, and develop their capacity for conflict resolution.

In particular, assignments enriched with national pedagogical heritage foster in students a sense of respect and pride for their own culture. This, in turn, positively impacts their personal and professional growth.

In statistical evaluations, the difference between the experimental and control groups is observed to be significantly high. While the experimental group showed a significant increase in the interaction index, communicative activity level, and collective responsibility indicators, these changes remained at a relatively low level in the control group. This scientifically confirms the effectiveness of the multi-vector approach.

From a pedagogical perspective, this approach ensures the comprehensive development of the student as an individual. It is aimed not only at imparting knowledge but also at forming social competencies. Karakalpak folk pedagogy contributes a spiritual and moral foundation, a spirit of social solidarity, and the values of community to this process. As a result, a synthesis of modern and national pedagogical traditions emerges.

Thus, improving students' collaborative skills based on a multi-vector approach is a strategic direction of the pedagogical process, which yields more stable and effective results when integrated with national values. This model serves to train competitive, socially responsible, and cooperation-ready specialists in higher education institutions.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, the development of students' collaborative skills based on multi-vector pedagogical approaches in educational processes has proven to be one of the important directions of the modern education system. In the process of collaborative learning, students not only acquire knowledge but also form important competencies such as social communication, teamwork, joint problem-solving, and decision-making.

From this perspective, applying a multi-vector approach in the educational process makes it possible to harmonize pedagogical, psychological, cultural, and social factors. An analysis of the experience of Karakalpak folk pedagogy shows that the people's educational traditions, formed over centuries, are based on the principles of collectivism, mutual assistance, and cooperation.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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Mas'ul muharrir: Ramzidin Ashurov

Ingliz tili muharriri: Murod Xoliyorov

Musahhih: Alibek Zokirov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

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